

Gender Equity and Women Representation in the Indian Parliament – A Study of the 17th General Elections

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: October

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2321-788X

E-ISSN: 2582-0397

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Arumugam, Anbu.
“Gender Equity and Women Representation in the Indian Parliament – A Study of the 17th General Elections.”
Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 28–33.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3549234>

Dr. Anbu Arumugam

Senior Assistant Professor

Department of Public Administration

Presidency College (Autonomous), Chennai

Background

Representation of women in decision making and administrative positions is an important indicator to measure the state of gender equality. Empowerment of women in all spheres including the political sphere is crucial for their advancement and for the foundation of a gender-neutral society. The global commitments India has ratified emphasise the need for women’s empowerment and gender equality as fundamental for achieving sustainable development outcomes at the policy level and grassroots level. The Millennium Development Goals (2000) and the Sustainable Development Goals (2016) consider women’s political participation of a country as an indicator for measuring gender equality related goals and targets.

Need for Study

Despite India moving a notch up in the latest Human Development Index (HDI) to rank 130 out of 189 countries and showing rapid progress in poverty eradication, inequality remains one of the pressing issues in the country as there is a decrease of 26.8% in the HDI value when adjusted for inequality (UNDP, 2019). The change in the value of India’s Inequality-adjusted HDI, which stood at 0.468, is far worse than the global average decline in the global HDI due to inequality at 20% (UNDP, 2019). India is ranked at 149 out of 191 countries for political participation of women in its national Parliament by the recently released report of the Inter-Parliamentary Union (IPU). According to the IPU report titled, “Women in Politics: 2019”, India’s average is 12.6% and 11.5% in the Lok Sabha and Rajya Sabha respectively (IPU, 2019). This is well below the world average of 24.3% and the regional average of Asia at 19.9%. in terms of women representation in both the houses of Parliament (IPU, 2019).

Methodology

This article is mainly based on secondary data obtained from various Government of India reports. Several articles and reports by international agencies have also been analysed in considering the state of women representation in Parliaments. The Election Commission of India data has been analysed for the time period from 1952 till 2019 with regards to the general elections conducted in India. The Census data has been covered till 2011 for women related statistics for the purpose of this article.

Review of Literature

India is considered to be ‘the largest democracy in the world’ and the Parliament is an important part of the political framework of this nation’s fabric. There is a gap in the literature in public administration on issues of gender and representation in the apex body of democracy with reference to India. Some of the literature relates to the descriptive histories of the Parliament (Gupta U., 2003) (Kashyap, 2008). The critical reviews on the Indian Parliament is another focus area for researchers and scholars (Shankar & Rodrigues, 2011) (Pai & Kumar (eds.), 2014). The literature that discusses the representation of women in legislature (Chopra, 1993) (Kumari & Dubey, 1994) have discussed the issue from the perspective of women’s empowerment in India. The possibilities for women participation in parliamentary democracy and the intersectionality’s are also discussed in some recent literature (Fadia, 2017)(M. Rai & Spary, 2019). Overall, the available literature indicates the need for more studies in this area.

Women in Indian Parliament – A Brief Analysis

India has a bi-cameral system with the Lok Sabha (Lower House) and Rajya Sabha (Upper House) like the British Parliamentary system. Women representation in the Parliament is very low at 12% in the Lok Sabha (Lower House) and 11% in the Rajya Sabha (Upper House). The Lok Sabha has 543 seats and Table 1 indicates the proportion of women MPs since the first general elections held in the year 1952. There is inadequate representation of women MPs in the Lower House of the Indian Parliament though there has been a marginal increase compared to the previous elections. As the data indicate only since the 2009 general elections the figures have touched double digit representation of women MPs.

Table 1 Women Representatives in the Lok Sabha

Year	Seats	Women MPs	% of Women MPs
1952	499	22	4.41
1957	500	27	5.40
1962	503	34	6.76
1967	523	31	5.93
1971	521	22	4.22
1977	544	19	3.29
1980	544	28	5.15
1984	544	44	8.9
1989	517	27	5.22
1991	544	39	7.17
1996	543	39	7.18
1998	543	43	7.92

1999	543	49	9.02
2004	543	45	8.03
2009	543	59	10.86
2014	543	66	12.6
2019	542	78	14.36

Source: Election Commission of India

The Rajya Sabha or the Upper House of the Parliament is like the House of Lords in the British Parliament, currently has 245 representatives. The number of women representatives in the Rajya Sabha has reduced from 31 in 2014 to 27 in 2016. The representation of women in the Council of Ministers in the central government has increased very marginally from 10% in 1985 to 12% in 2018 (MoSPI, GOI, 2019). The local governance or the Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) have women representation of 46% across the 640 districts in India (MoSPI, GOI, 2019). This development has mainly been due to legislative stipulation of 33% reservation of seats to women.

Women in the 17th General Elections in India

The 17th General Elections held to the Lok Sabha of the Parliament were organised by the Election Commission of India (ECI), which is the apex body sanctioned by the Constitution of India for the conduct of elections in India. The newly elected house boasts of 78 women MPs compared to the 62 women MPs elected to the 16th Lok Sabha in 2014 (ECI, 2019). The first-ever general elections held in 1952 saw 5% women MPs in the House and the representation has steadily increased to 14% in the current general elections held in India in 2019 (ECI, 2017). Though the percentage of women MPs has increased over the years, it is still lower in comparison to some countries. These include Rwanda (61%), South Africa (43%), UK (32%), USA (24%), Bangladesh (21%) (IPU, 2019). The BJP accounts for most of the women MPs with 42, followed by the Trinamool Congress with seven and the Biju Janata Dal with six. The BJP's sweep and the Biju Janata Dal's stated commitment to gender equity by fielding 33% women candidates are the key reasons for the rise in the share of women MPs. Nearly half of all women MPs come from just four states – 14% from Uttar Pradesh, 12.8% from West Bengal, 10.3% from Maharashtra and 9% from Odisha. A brief analysis of data from the Parliament show that of the 543 constituencies nearly 48.4% have never voted for a woman MP since 1962 (ECI, 2017). The trend that needs to be observed is that the proportion of seats contested by women was a dismal 3.73% at the national level in 1991 General Elections and has very marginally gone up to 8% in the 2014 General Elections held in India (ECI, 2017).

The total number of contestants were 8,049 candidates for the 543 seats in the 17th Lok Sabha. Overall 724 women candidates were given tickets to contest the general elections by the political parties (ECI, 2019). Analysing the political manifestos of India's major national political parties in the run up to the 2019 General Elections to elect the 17th Lok Sabha brings out the positioning of women in their agendas. The two major national parties INC and BJP fielded 54 and 53 women candidates respectively. Among other national parties the Bahujan Samaj Party (BSP) fielded 24 women candidates, the All India Trinamool Congress (AITC) 23, the Communist Party of India (Marxist) 10, the Communist Party of India (CPI) 4, while the Nationalist Congress Party (NCP) fielded one-woman candidate. These are absolute numbers and a closer look at the data indicates the proportion is indeed nowhere close to the 33% reservation these political parties propose in their political manifestos.

Findings

This research article focussed on available secondary research and data across several government agencies with regards to the main theme of women representation in the Indian Parliament. The major findings are as follows:

1. There is a marginal increase in the representation of women in the Indian Parliament in the 17th General Elections held in May 2019. This is in comparison to the previous elections held in 2014.
2. The number of seats contested by women in the elections to the Lok Sabha (Lower House) has also seen a marginal increase in the 17th General Elections in comparison to the previous elections held in 2014.
3. The major national parties of India according to the Election Commission of India have declared in their Election Manifestos a poll promise of bringing in the Women's Reservation Bill in the Parliament.
4. The apex planning body for India, NITI Aayog's policy documents does not dwell into the representation of women in the Indian Parliament. The target set by NITI Aayog is to increase the strength of women representation in the State Legislative Assemblies to 50% by the year 2030.

Recommendations

The paper has analysed the historical basis, facts and evolving trends of this issue with relevance to India. This paper proposes the following recommendations for consideration by the authorities concerned with regards to the issue of underrepresentation of women in Indian Parliament.

- The Women's Reservation Bill can be seen a direct policy mechanism to address this issue. The Government of India needs to come out with a policy document regarding the status of representation of women in the Indian Parliament.
- The agenda of 'One Nation One Election' needs to be reworked integrate the issue of women representation in the Parliament and State Legislative Assemblies to avoid duplication of the processes.
- A nodal agency could be setup to explore the ways and means of increasing the presence of women in the Parliament. The Ministry of Parliamentary Affairs or the Ministry for Women and Child Development or the Law Commission and the Election Commission of India along with the NITI Aayog could be entrusted with this task.

Conclusion

India has come a long way since independence towards women empowerment across different parameters. The idea of increased presence of women in the highest decision-making bodies of India has become a constant through populist demands, increased awareness among the general electorate, global commitments and ratifications, initiatives by some national parties by way of voluntary seat-allocation and so on. The agenda of women's representation in the Indian Parliament is an important step in ensuring adequate participation of women in the electoral process than as electorates. The world's largest democracy has a definitive responsibility in initiating a clear roadmap in addressing this issue in alignment with the Sustainable Development Goals. The Indian democracy needs a renewed push and electoral reforms in favour of women for a gender-neutral policy paradigm.

References

1. Census. (2011). Census Data. Ministry of Home Affairs, Government of India, Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, India, New Delhi. Retrieved April 2019, from <http://censusindia.gov.in/2011-Common/CensusData2011.html>
2. Chopra, J. (1993). *Women in the Indian Parliament*. New Delhi: Mittal Publications.
3. Dahlerup, D., Hilal, Z., Kalandadze, N., & Kandawasvika-Nhundu, R. (2014). *Atlas of Electoral Gender Quotas*. Stockholm: Inter-Parliamentary Union, Stockholm University. Retrieved July 2019, from <https://www.idea.int/sites/default/files/publications/atlas-of-electoral-gender-quotas.pdf>
4. ECI. (2017). *Electoral Statistics Pocket Book*. Election Commission of India, Government of India, New Delhi. Retrieved April 2019, from <https://www.eci.gov.in/>
5. ECI. (2019, March 10). Election Commission of India. Retrieved from Election Commission of India: <https://eci.gov.in>
6. Fadia, K. (2017, October 4). Women's Empowerment Through Political Participation in India. *Indian Journal of Public Administration*, 60(3), 537-548. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/0019556120140313>
7. Gupta, U. (2003). *Indian Parliamentary Democracy*. Atlantic Publishers & Distributors.
8. IPU. (2019). *Women in Parliament 2018: The Year in Review*. Inter Parliamentary Union. Retrieved from <https://www.ipu.org/resources/publications/reports/2019-03/women-in-parliament-in-2018-year-in-review>
9. IPU. (2019). *Women in Politics:2019*. Inter-Parliamentary Union. Retrieved May 2019, from <https://www.ipu.org/resources/publications/infographics/2019-03/women-in-politics-2019>
10. Jayal, N. G. (2006). *Representing India: Ethnic Diversity and the Governance of Public Institutions*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
11. Jayal, N. G. (2013). *Citizenship and Its Discontents: An Indian History*. New Delhi: Permanent Black.
12. Kashyap, S. (2008). *History of the Parliament of India*. Delhi: Radha Publications.
13. Kumari, R., & Dubey, A. (1994). *Women Parliamentarians: A Study in the Indian Context*. New Delhi: Har-Anand Publications.
14. M. Rai, S., & Spary, C. (2019). *Performing Representation Women Members in the Indian Parliament*. New Delhi: Oxford University Press.
15. Menon, R., & Bhasin, K. (1998). *Borders and Boundaries*. New Jersey: Rutgers University Press.
16. MoSPI, GOI. (2019). *Women and Men in India 2018*. New Delhi: Social Statistics Division, Central Statistics Office, Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Government of India. Retrieved April 2019, from http://www.mospi.gov.in/sites/default/files/publication_reports/Women%20and%20Men%20in%20India%202018.pdf
17. NITI Aayog. (2017). *India Three Year Action Agenda*. Government of India, NITI Aayog. New Delhi: NITI Aayog, Government of India. Retrieved November 23, 2018, from <http://www.niti.gov.in>
18. NITI Aayog. (2018). *SDG India Index Baseline Report*. Government of India, NITI Aayog. New Delhi: NITI Aayog. Retrieved January 2019, from <http://www.niti.gov.in>
19. NITI Aayog. (2018). *Strategy for New India @ 75*. New Delhi: NITI Aayog. Retrieved https://niti.gov.in/writereaddata/files/Strategy_for_New_India.pdf April 2019
20. Pai, S., & Kumar (eds.), A. (2014). *The Indian Parliament: A Critical Appraisal*. Hyderabad: Orient BlackSwan.

21. Sachs, J.-T. K. (2019). SDG Index and Dashboards Report 2019. New York: Bertelsmann Stiftung and Sustainable Development Solutions Network (SDSN). Retrieved July 2019, from https://s3.amazonaws.com/sustainabledevelopment.report/2019/2019_sustainable_development_report.pdf
22. Shankar, B., & Rodrigues, V. (2011). The Indian Parliament: A Democracy at Work. Oxford University Press.
23. UNDP. (2019). Retrieved June 2019, from United Nations Development Program: <http://hdr.undp.org/en/composite/IHDI>
24. WCW, B. (1995). Fourth World Conference on Women. New Delhi: Department of Women and Child Development, Ministry of Human Resource Development, Government of India.
25. WEF. (2019). Global Gender Gap Report 2018. Geneva, Switzerland: World Economic Forum. Retrieved April 2019